

Intuitionistic Fuzzy BZ-Ideals in BZ-algebra

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Abstract

We consider the intuitionistic fuzzification of the concept BZ-ideal and some fundamental properties to BZ-algebra are discussed and the image (pre-image) of BZ-ideal in BZ-algebra, and investigate some of these properties. Moreover, we introduce the notion of Cartesian product of intuitionistic fuzzy BZ-ideal in BZ-algebras, and investigate some related properties.

Keywords

BZ-algebras, fuzzy BZ-ideals, intuitionistic fuzzy BZ-ideal, image (pre-image) of BZ-ideal, Cartesian product.

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INTRODUCTION

W.A. Dudek introduced new of abstract algebras: is called BCC-algebras as a generalization of the concept of set-theoretic difference and propositional calculus and studied some important properties in ([1-6]). In this paper, we introduce new of abstract algebras: is called ARZ-algebras which is a generalization of the concept BCC-algebra and define its subalgebras ideals, atom, star and ARZ-ideals of ARZ-algebra. We study quotient of ARZ-algebra and describe its properties. Also, we introduce homomorphism of its.

2. The Structure of BZ-algebras

In this section we include some elementary aspects necessary for this paper

Definition 2.1([18,19]). Let $(X; *, 0)$ be an algebra with operation $(+)$ and constant (0) . X is called a BZ-algebra if it satisfies the following identities: for any $x, y, z \in X$,

(BZ-1) $((x * z) * (y * z)) * (x * y) = 0$;

(BZ-2) $x * 0 = x$;

(BZ-3) $x * y = 0$ and $y * x = 0$ implies that $x = y$.

Remark 2.2. ([18,19]).

On BZ -algebra $(X, *, 0)$, we defined a binary relation \leq on X by putting $x \leq y$ if and only if $x * y = 0$.

Proposition 2.3 ([1-3,18,19]). . Let $(X; *, 0)$ be a BZ-algebra, then (X, \leq) is a partially ordered set. It is easy to show that the following properties are true for a BZ -algebra. For any $x, y, z \in X$:

- (P-1) $x * ((x * y) * y) = 0$;
(P-2) $x * x = 0$;
(P-3) $x * (y * z) = y * (x * z)$;
(P-4) $((x * y) * y) * y = x * y$;
(P-5) $(x * y) * 0 = (x * 0) * (y * 0)$;
(P-6) $(x * y) * ((z * x) * (z * y)) = 0$;
(P-7) $x \leq y$ implies $y * z \leq x * z$;
(P-8) $x \leq y$ implies $z * x \leq z * y$.

Definition 2.4. ([19]). A subset S of a BZ -algebra X is called **subalgebra of X** if $x * y \in S$ whenever $x, y \in S$.

Definition 2.5. ([1-3]). A non-empty subset I of a BZ -algebra $(X; *, 0)$ is called **BZ -ideal of X** if it satisfies the following conditions: for any $x, y, z \in X$

- (I-1) $0 \in I$
(I-2) $(x * y) * z \in I$ and $y \in I$ imply $x * z \in I$.

Definition 2.6. ([7]). Let I be an ideal of BZ -algebra $(X, *, 0)$. Define the relation \sim on X by $x \sim y$ if and only if $x * y \in I$ and $y * x \in I$. Then the relation \sim is an equivalence relation on X and $[0]_I = \{x \in X \mid x \sim 0\}$ is an ideal of X .

Remark 2.7 ([7]). Let \sim be an equivalence relation on a BZ -algebra $(X, *, 0)$ and I be an ideal of X . Define $[x]_I$ by $[x]_I = \{y \in X \mid x \sim y\} = \{y \in X \mid x * y \in I, y * x \in I\}$, then the family $[x]_I \mid x \in X$ gives a partition of X which is denoted by X/I .

For any $x, y \in X$, we defined $[x]_I \circ [y]_I = [x * y]_I$, then the binary operation \circ is a mapping from $X/I \times X/I$ to X/I .

It is easily checked that $(X/I, \circ, [0]_I)$ is a BZ -algebra. Moreover, the set X/I is called the **quotient BZ -algebra**. And if I is an ideal of BZ -algebra X , then it is clear that $[a]_I = I$ for all a in I .

Proposition 2.8 ([18,19]). Every BZ -ideal of BZ -algebra $(X, *, 0)$ is a subalgebra of X .

Proposition 2.9 ([18,19]). Let $\{I_i \mid i \in \Lambda\}$ be a family of ideals of BZ -algebra $(X, *, 0)$. The intersection of any set of BZ -ideals of X is also an BZ -ideal of X .

Definition 2.10 ([10]). Let $(X, *, 0)$ and $(Y, *', 0')$ be nonempty sets. The mapping $f : (X, *, 0) \rightarrow (Y, *', 0')$ is called a **homomorphism** if it satisfies:

$f(x * y) = f(x) *' f(y)$, for all $x, y \in X$. The set $\{x \in X \mid f(x) = 0'\}$ is called the **kernel of f** denoted by $\ker f$.

Theorem 2.11 ([1-3]). Let $f : (X, *, 0) \rightarrow (Y, *', 0')$ be a homomorphism of a BZ -algebra X into an BZ -algebra Y , then:

- (1) $f(0) = 0'$.
(2) f is injective if and only if $\ker f = \{0\}$.
(3) $x \leq y$ implies $f(x) \leq f(y)$.

Theorem 2.12 ([1-3]). Let $f : (X, *, 0) \rightarrow (Y, *', 0')$ be a homomorphism of an BZ -algebra X into an BZ -algebra Y , then :

- (F₁) If S is a subalgebra of X , then $f(S)$ is a subalgebra of Y .
(F₂) If I is BZ -ideal of X , then $f(I)$ is BZ -ideal in Y .
(F₃) If D is a subalgebra of Y , then $f^{-1}(D)$ is a subalgebra of X .
(F₄) If J is BZ -ideal in Y , then $f^{-1}(J)$ is BZ -ideal in X .
(F₅) $\ker f$ is BZ -ideal of X .
(F₆) $\text{Im}(f)$ is a subalgebra of Y .

Definition 2.13([23]). Let $(X, *, 0)$ be a nonempty set, a fuzzy subset μ of X is a mapping $\mu : X \rightarrow [0, 1]$.

Definition 2.14. [23] Let μ be a fuzzy subset of a set X . For $t \in [0, 1]$, the set $\mu_t = U(\mu, t) = \{x \in X \mid \mu(x) \geq t\}$, is called upper level cut (level subset) of μ and the set $L(\mu, t) = \{x \in X \mid \mu(x) \leq t\}$ is called lower level cut of μ .

Definition 2.15 ([9]).

Let $f : (X, *, 0) \rightarrow (Y, *', 0')$ be a mapping nonempty sets X and Y respectively. If μ is a fuzzy subset of X , then the fuzzy subset β of Y defined by:

$$f(\mu)(y) = \begin{cases} \sup\{\mu(x) : x \in f^{-1}(y)\} & \text{if } f^{-1}(y) = \{x \in X, f(x) = y\} \neq \emptyset \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

is said to be the image of μ under f .

Similarly if β is a fuzzy subset of Y , then the fuzzy subset $\mu = (\beta \circ f)$ of X (i.e the fuzzy subset defined by $\mu(x) = \beta(f(x))$ for all $x \in X$) is called the pre-image of β under f .

Definition 2.16 ([9]).

A fuzzy subset μ of a set X has **sup property** if for any subset T of X , there exist $t_0 \in T$ such that $\mu(t_0) = \sup\{\mu(t) \mid t \in T\}$.

Definition 2.17([1,18]). Let $(X, *, 0)$ be an BZ -algebra, a fuzzy subset μ of X is called a **fuzzy subalgebra of X** if for all $x, y \in X$, $\mu(x * y) \geq \min\{\mu(x), \mu(y)\}$

Proposition 2.18([1,19]). Let μ be a fuzzy subset of BZ -algebra $(X, *, 0)$. If μ is a fuzzy subalgebra of X , then for any t

$\in [0,1]$, μ_t is a subalgebra of X .

Definition 2.19. [5]. Let $(X; *, 0)$ be an BZ-algebra. A fuzzy subset μ of X is called a **fuzzy BZ-ideal of X** if it satisfies the following conditions: for all $x, y \in X$,

- (1) $\mu(0) \geq \mu(x)$.
- (2) $\mu(x * z) \geq \min\{\mu((x * y) * z), \mu(y)\}$.

Proposition 2.20[5]. Every fuzzy BZ-ideal of BZ-algebra is fuzzy subalgebra.

Proposition 2.21 ([5]). Let $f: (X; *, 0) \rightarrow (Y; *, 0)$ be a homomorphism between BZ-algebras X and Y respectively.

- 1- For every fuzzy subalgebra β of Y , $f^{-1}(\beta)$ is a fuzzy subalgebra of X .
- 2- For every fuzzy subalgebra μ of X , $f(\mu)$ is a fuzzy subalgebra of Y .
- 3- For every fuzzy BZ-ideal β of Y , $f^{-1}(\beta)$ is a fuzzy BZ-ideal of X .
- 4- For every fuzzy BZ-ideal μ of X with sup property, $f(\mu)$ is a fuzzy BZ-ideal of Y , where f is onto.

3. Intuitionistic fuzzy BZ-ideal in BZ-algebra.

In this section, we shall define the notion of intuitionistic fuzzy BZ-ideals in BZ-algebra and we study its properties when the intuitionistic fuzzy BZ-algebra is replace with intuitionistic fuzzy BZ-ideal of BZ-algebra X .

Definition 3.1([6]). An intuitionistic fuzzy subset A in a nonempty set X is an object having the form $A = \{(x, \mu_A(x), \nu_A(x)) \mid x \in X\}$ where the functions $\mu_A: X \rightarrow [0,1]$ and $\nu_A: X \rightarrow [0,1]$ denote the fuzzy function and the degree of doubt fuzzy function respectively and $0 \leq \mu_A(x) + \nu_A(x) \leq 1$, for all $x \in X$.

Remark 3.2([6]). If an intuitionistic fuzzy subset A in a nonempty set X , then $\mu_A(x) + \nu_A(x) = 1$, i.e., when $\nu_A(x) = 1 - \mu_A(x) = \mu_A^c(x)$ for all $x \in X$. Then μ_A is called a fuzzy subset and $\nu_A = \mu_A^c$ is the complement of μ_A .

Definition 3.3. Let $A = \{(x, \mu_A(x), \nu_A(x)) \mid x \in X\}$ be an intuitionistic fuzzy subset of a BZ-algebra X . A is said to be an intuitionistic fuzzy Subalgebra of X if: for all $x, y \in X$,

- (IFS₁) $\mu_A(x * y) \geq \min\{\mu_A(x), \mu_A(y)\}$.
- (IFS₂) $\nu_A(x * y) \leq \max\{\nu_A(x), \nu_A(y)\}$.

Example 3.4. Let $X = \{0, 1, 2, 3\}$ in which $(*)$ is defined by the following table :

*	0	1	2	3
0	0	1	2	3
1	1	0	3	2
2	2	3	0	1
3	3	2	1	0

It is easy to show that $(X; *, 0)$ is BZ-algebra.

$A = \{(x, \mu_A(x), \nu_A(x)) \mid x \in X\}$ is intuitionistic fuzzy subset of X defined by: $\mu_A(0) = \mu_A(2) = 0.6 > 0.2 = \mu_A(1) = \mu_A(3)$, and $\nu_A(0) = \nu_A(2) = 0.1 < 0.7 = \nu_A(1) = \nu_A(3)$. Then A is an intuitionistic fuzzy Subalgebra of X .

Proposition 3.5. Every intuitionistic fuzzy subalgebra

$A = \{(x, \mu_A(x), \nu_A(x)) \mid x \in X\}$ of a BZ-algebra X satisfies the inequalities

$$\mu_A(0) \geq \mu_A(x) \text{ and } \nu_A(0) \leq \nu_A(x), \text{ for all } x \in X.$$

Proof. $\mu_A(0) = \mu_A(x * x) \geq \min\{\mu_A(x), \mu_A(x)\} = \mu_A(x)$ and $\nu_A(0) = \nu_A(x * x) \leq \max\{\nu_A(x), \nu_A(x)\} = \nu_A(x)$. \square

Definition 3.6. Let $A = \{(x, \mu_A(x), \nu_A(x)) \mid x \in X\}$ be an intuitionistic fuzzy subset of a BZ-algebra X . A is said to be an intuitionistic fuzzy BZ-ideal of X if: for all $x, y, z \in X$,

- (IFAT₁) $\mu_A(0) \geq \mu_A(x)$ and $\nu_A(0) \leq \nu_A(x)$,
- (IFAT₂) $\mu_A(x * z) \geq \min\{\mu_A((x * y) * z), \mu_A(y)\}$ and $\nu_A(x * z) \leq \max\{\nu_A((x * y) * z), \nu_A(y)\}$.

Example 3.7. Let $X = \{0, 1, 2, 3\}$ as in example (3.4). Define

$A = \{(x, \mu_A(x), \nu_A(x)) \mid x \in X\}$ in X as follows in which $(*)$ is defined by the following table : $\mu_A(0) = \mu_A(2) = 1$, $\mu_A(1) = \mu_A(3) = t$, and

$v_A(0) = v_A(2) = 0$, $v_A(1) = v_A(3) = s$ where $t, s \in [0, 1]$ and $t + s \leq 1$. By routine calculations we know that A is an intuitionistic fuzzy BZ-ideal of X .

Definition 3.8([6]). For any $t \in [0, 1]$ and a fuzzy subset μ in a nonempty set X , the set $U(\mu, t) = \{x \in X \mid \mu(x) \geq t\}$ is called an upper t -level cut of μ , and the set $L(\mu, t) = \{x \in X \mid \mu(x) \leq t\}$ is called a lower t -level cut of μ .

Theorem 3.9. An intuitionistic fuzzy subset

$A = \{(x, \mu_A(x), \nu_A(x)) \mid x \in X\}$ is an intuitionistic fuzzy subalgebra of a BZ-algebra X if and only if for all $s, t \in [0, 1]$, the set $U(\mu_A, t)$ and $L(\nu_A, s)$ are subalgebras of X .

Proof. Let $A = \{(x, \mu_A(x), \nu_A(x)) \mid x \in X\}$ be an intuitionistic fuzzy subalgebra of X and $U(\mu_A, t) \neq \emptyset \neq L(\nu_A, s)$.

It follows that for all $x, y \in X$ such that $x \in U(\mu_A, t)$, $y \in U(\mu_A, t)$, then $\mu_A(x) \geq t$ and $\mu_A(y) \geq t$, it follows that $\mu_A(x * y) \geq \min\{\mu_A(x), \mu_A(y)\} \geq t$, so that $(x * y) \in U(\mu_A, t)$.

Hence $U(\mu_A, t)$ is a subalgebra of X .

In a similar way, we can prove that $L(\nu_A, s)$ is a subalgebra of X .

Conversely, assume that for each $s, t \in [0, 1]$, the sets $U(\mu_A, t)$ and $L(\nu_A, s)$ are subalgebras of X . If there exist $x', y' \in X$ be such that

$\mu_A(x' * y') < \min\{\mu_A(x'), \mu_A(y')\}$, then by taking

$t_0 = \frac{1}{2}\{\mu_A(x' * y') + \min\{\mu_A(x'), \mu_A(y')\}\}$, we get

$\mu_A(x' * y') < t_0 < \min\{\mu_A(x'), \mu_A(y')\}$ and hence $(x' * y') \notin U(\mu_A, t_0)$, $x' \in U(\mu_A, t_0)$, $y' \in U(\mu_A, t_0)$, i.e., $U(\mu_A, t_0)$, is not a subalgebra of X , which make a contradiction.

Finally assume $\nu_A(x' * y') > \max\{\nu_A(x'), \nu_A(y')\}$, then by taking $s_0 = \frac{1}{2}\{\nu_A(x' * y') +$

$\max\{\nu_A(x'), \nu_A(y')\}\}$, we get $\max\{\nu_A(x'), \nu_A(y')\} > s_0 > \nu_A(x' * y')$ and hence

$(x' * y') \notin L(\nu_A, s_0)$, $x' \in L(\nu_A, s_0)$, $y' \in L(\nu_A, s_0)$, i.e., $L(\nu_A, s_0)$, is not a subalgebra of BZ-algebra X , which make a contradiction.

Hence $A = \{(x, \mu_A(x), \nu_A(x)) \mid x \in X\}$ is an intuitionistic fuzzy subalgebra of X . \triangle

Theorem 3.10. An intuitionistic fuzzy subset

$A = \{(x, \mu_A(x), \nu_A(x)) \mid x \in X\}$ is an intuitionistic fuzzy BZ-ideal of a BZ-algebra X if and only if for all $s, t \in [0, 1]$, the set $U(\mu_A, t)$ and $L(\nu_A, s)$ are BZ-ideals of X .

Proof.

Let $A = \{(x, \mu_A(x), \nu_A(x)) \mid x \in X\}$ be an intuitionistic fuzzy BZ-ideal of X and $U(\mu_A, t) \neq \emptyset \neq L(\nu_A, s)$.

Since $\mu_A(0) \geq t$ and $\nu_A(0) \leq s$, let $x, y, z \in X$ be such that $((x * y) * z) \in U(\mu_A, t)$, $(y) \in U(\mu_A, t)$, then $\mu_A((x * y) * z) \geq t$ and $\mu_A(y) \geq t$, it follows that $\mu_A(x * z) \geq \min\{\mu_A((x * y) * z), \mu_A(y)\} \geq t$, so that $(x * z) \in U(\mu_A, t)$.

Hence $U(\mu_A, t)$ is a BZ-ideal of X .

In a similar way, we can prove that $L(\nu_A, s)$ is a BZ-ideal of X .

Conversely, assume that for each $s, t \in [0, 1]$, the sets $U(\mu_A, t)$ and $L(\nu_A, s)$ are BZ-ideals of X . For any $x \in X$, let $\mu_A(x) = t$ and $\nu_A(x) = s$. Then $x \in U(\mu_A, t) \cap L(\nu_A, s)$ and so $U(\mu_A, t) \neq \emptyset \neq L(\nu_A, s)$.

Since $U(\mu_A, t)$ and $L(\nu_A, s)$ are BZ-ideals of X , therefore

$0 \in U(\mu_A, t) \cap L(\nu_A, s)$. Hence $\mu_A(0) \geq t = \mu_A(x)$ and

$\nu_A(0) \leq s = \nu_A(x)$, for all $x \in X$.

If there exist $x', y', z' \in X$ be such that $\mu_A(x' * z') < \min\{\mu_A((x' * y') * z'), \mu_A(y')\}$, then by taking

$t_0 = \frac{1}{2}\{\mu_A(x' * z') + \min\{\mu_A((x' * y') * z'), \mu_A(y')\}\}$, we get

$\mu_A(x' * z') < t_0 < \min\{\mu_A((x' * y') * z'), \mu_A(y')\}$ and hence $(x' * z') \notin U(\mu_A, t_0)$,

$((x' * y') * z') \in U(\mu_A, t_0)$, $(y') \in U(\mu_A, t_0)$, i.e., $U(\mu_A, t_0)$, is not a BZ-ideal of X , which make a contradiction.

Finally assume that there exist $x', y', z' \in X$ such that

$\nu_A(x' * z') > \max\{\nu_A((x' * y') * z'), \nu_A(y')\}$. Then by taking

$s_0 = \frac{1}{2}\{\nu_A(x' * z') + \max\{\nu_A((x' * y') * z'), \nu_A(y')\}\}$, we get $\max\{\nu_A((x' * y') * z'), \nu_A(y')\} > s_0 > \nu_A(x' * z')$ and hence

$(x' * z') \notin L(\nu_A, s_0)$, $((x' * y') * z') \in L(\nu_A, s_0)$, $(y') \in L(\nu_A, s_0)$, i.e., $L(\nu_A, s_0)$, is not a BZ-ideal of BZ-algebra X , which make a contradiction.

Hence $A = \{(x, \mu_A(x), \nu_A(x)) \mid x \in X\}$ is an intuitionistic fuzzy BZ-ideal of X . \triangle

Proposition 3.11. Let $A = \{(x, \mu_A(x), \nu_A(x)) \mid x \in X\}$ be an intuitionistic fuzzy BZ-ideal of BZ-algebra X , then A is an intuitionistic fuzzy subalgebra of X .

Proof: Since A be a an intuitionistic fuzzy BZ-ideal of X of a BZ-algebra X , then for all $s, t \in [0, 1]$, the set $U(\mu_A, t)$ and $L(\nu_A, s)$ are BZ-ideals of X by Proposition (3.10). By Proposition (2.8), for all $s, t \in [0, 1]$, the set $U(\mu_A, t)$ and $L(\nu_A, s)$ are subalgebras of X .

Therefore, $A = \{(x, \mu_A(x), \nu_A(x)) \mid x \in X\}$ is an intuitionistic fuzzy subalgebra of X by Proposition (3.9). \triangle

4. Homomorphism of Intuitionistic fuzzy BZ-ideal in BZ-algebra:

Definition 4.1[6]. Let $(X, *, 0)$ and $(Y, *, '0')$ be two nonempty sets. A mapping $f : X \rightarrow Y$ is said to be a homomorphism if $f(x * y) = f(x) *' f(y)$ for all $x, y \in X$.

Note that if $f : X \rightarrow Y$ is a homomorphism of sets, then $f(0) = '0'$.

Definition 4.2. Let $f : (X; *, 0) \rightarrow (Y; *, '0')$ be a homomorphism of BZ-algebras for any $A = \{(y, \mu_A(y), \nu_A(y)) \mid y \in Y\}$ in Y , we define new $A^f = \{(x, \mu_A^f(x), \nu_A^f(x)) \mid x \in X\}$ in X by $\mu_A^f(x) = \mu_A(f(x))$ and $\nu_A^f(x) = \nu_A(f(x))$ for all $x \in X$.

Theorem 4.3. Let $f : (X; *, 0) \rightarrow (Y; *, '0')$ be an epimorphism of a BZ-algebra X into a BZ-algebra Y , then :

- (1) If $A = \{(x, \mu_A(x), \nu_A(x)) \mid x \in X\}$ is an intuitionistic fuzzy subalgebra in X , then the image of A is an intuitionistic fuzzy subalgebra in Y .
- (2) If $A = \{(x, \mu_A(x), \nu_A(x)) \mid x \in X\}$ is an intuitionistic fuzzy BZ-ideal in X , then the image of A is an intuitionistic fuzzy BZ-ideal in Y .

Proof.

1- We show that the image of A is an intuitionistic fuzzy subalgebra in Y . Since A is an intuitionistic fuzzy subalgebra in X and for any $a, b \in X$ there exist $x, y \in Y$ such that $f(a) = x, f(b) = y$, then

$$\begin{aligned} \mu_A(x *' y) &= \mu_A(f(a) *' f(b)) \\ &\geq \min\{\mu_A(f(a)), \mu_A(f(b))\} \\ &= \min\{\mu_A(x), \mu_A(y)\}, \text{ and} \\ \nu_A(x *' y) &= \nu_A(f(a) *' f(b)) \\ &\leq \max\{\nu_A(f(a)), \nu_A(f(b))\} \\ &= \max\{\nu_A(x), \nu_A(y)\}. \end{aligned}$$

Hence the image of A is an intuitionistic fuzzy subalgebra in Y .

2- We show that the image of A is an intuitionistic fuzzy BZ-ideal in Y . Then $\mu_A(f(x)) \leq \mu_A(f(0))$, and $\nu_A(f(x)) \geq \nu_A(f(0))$, for all $x \in X$.

Let $a, b, c \in X$ and $x, y, z \in Y$ such that $f(a) = x, f(b) = y,$

$f(c) = z$, then

$$\begin{aligned} \mu_A(a *' c) &= \mu_A(f(x) *' f(z)) \\ &\geq \min\{\mu_A(f(x) *' (f(y) *' f(z))), \mu_A f(y)\} \\ &= \min\{\mu_A(a *' (b *' c)), \mu_A(b)\} \text{ and} \\ \nu_A(a *' c) &= \nu_A(f(x) *' f(z)) \\ &\leq \max\{\nu_A(f(x) *' (f(y) *' f(z))), \nu_A f(y)\} \\ &= \max\{\nu_A(a *' (b *' c)), \nu_A(b)\}. \end{aligned}$$

Hence the image of A is an intuitionistic fuzzy BZ-ideal in Y .

Theorem 4.4. Let $f : (X; *, 0) \rightarrow (Y; *, '0')$ be a homomorphism of a BZ-algebra X into a BZ-algebra Y , then :

(1) If A is an intuitionistic fuzzy subalgebra in Y , then

$A^f = \{(x, \mu_A^f(x), \nu_A^f(x)) \mid x \in X\}$ is an intuitionistic fuzzy subalgebra in X .

(2) If A is an intuitionistic fuzzy BZ-ideal in Y , then

$A^f = \{(x, \mu_A^f(x), \nu_A^f(x)) \mid x \in X\}$ is an intuitionistic fuzzy BZ-ideal in X .

Proof.

1- We show that A^f is an intuitionistic fuzzy subalgebra in X . Since A is an intuitionistic fuzzy subalgebra in Y and let

$x, y \in X$,

$$\begin{aligned} \mu_A^f(A)(x * y) &= \mu_A(f(x * y)) \\ &= \mu_A(f(x) *' f(y)) \\ &\geq \min\{\mu_A(f(x)), \mu_A(f(y))\} \\ &= \min\{\mu_A^f(A)(x), \mu_A^f(A)(y)\}, \text{ and} \\ \nu_A^f(A)(x * y) &= \nu_A(f(x * y)) \\ &= \nu_A(f(x) *' f(y)) \\ &\leq \max\{\nu_A(f(x)), \nu_A(f(y))\} \\ &= \max\{\nu_A^f(A)(x), \nu_A^f(A)(y)\}. \end{aligned}$$

Hence A^f is an intuitionistic fuzzy subalgebra in X .

2- We show that A^f is an intuitionistic fuzzy BZ-ideal in X . Since A is an intuitionistic fuzzy BZ-ideal in Y and for any $a, b, c \in X$ there exist $x, y, z \in Y$ such that $f(a) = x, f(b) = y, f(c) = z$, then

$$\begin{aligned}
\mu_A(f(a)) &= \mu_A(x) \leq \mu_A(0') = \mu_A(f(0)), \text{ and} \\
\nu_A(f(a)) &= \nu_A(x) \geq \nu_A(0') = \nu_A(f(0)), \text{ for all } a \in X. \text{ And} \\
\mu_A^f(a * c) &= \mu_A(f(a * c)) \\
&= \mu_A(f(a) * ' f(c)) \\
&= \mu_A(x * ' z) \\
&\geq \min\{\mu_A(x * '(y * ' z)), \mu_A(y)\} \\
&= \min\{(\mu_A(f(a) * '(f(b) * ' f(c))), \mu_A f(b))\} \\
&= \min\{\mu_A(f * (a * (b * c))), \mu_A f(b)\} \\
&= \min\{\mu_A^f(a * (b * c)), \mu_A^f(b)\}, \text{ and} \\
\nu_A^f(a * c) &= \nu_A(f(a * c)) \\
&= \nu_A(f(a) * ' f(c)) \\
&= \nu_A(x * ' z) \\
&\leq \max\{\nu_A(a * '(b * ' c)), \nu_A(y)\} \\
&= \max\{\nu_A(f(a) * '(f(b) * ' f(c))), \nu_A f(b)\} \\
&= \max\{\nu_A(f(a * (b * c))), \nu_A f(b)\} \\
&= \max\{\nu_A^f(a * (b * c)), \nu_A^f(b)\}.
\end{aligned}$$

Hence A^f is an intuitionistic fuzzy BZ-ideal in X . \triangle

5. Cartesian product of intuitionistic fuzzy KUS-ideal

In this section, we will discuss, investigate a new notion called cartesian product of intuitionistic fuzzy BZ-ideals and we study several basic properties which related to intuitionistic fuzzy BZ-ideals.

Definition 5.1[6]. Let β and λ be are two fuzzy subsets in the set $(X; *, 0)$. the cartesian product $\beta \times \lambda : X \times X \rightarrow [0,1]$ is defined by

$$\beta \times \lambda(x, y) = \min\{\beta(x), \lambda(y)\}, \text{ for all } x, y \in X.$$

Definition 5.2[6].

Let $A = \{(x, \beta_A(x), \lambda_A(x)) \mid x \in X\}$ and $B = \{(x, \beta_B(x), \lambda_B(x)) \mid x \in X\}$ are two intuitionistic fuzzy subsets of X , the cartesian product

$A \times B = (X \times X, \beta_A \times \beta_B, \lambda_A \times \lambda_B)$ such that

$\beta_A \times \beta_B : X \times X \rightarrow [0,1]$ is defined by

$$(\beta_A \times \beta_B)(x, y) = \min\{\beta_A(x), \beta_B(y)\} \text{ and}$$

$\lambda_A \times \lambda_B : X \times X \rightarrow [0,1]$ is defined by

$$(\lambda_A \times \lambda_B)(x, y) = \max\{\lambda_A(x), \lambda_B(y)\} \text{ for all } x, y \in X.$$

Remark 5.3. Let $(X; *, 0)$ and $(Y; *, 0)$ be BZ-algebras, we define $(*)$ on $X \times Y$ by: For every $(x, y), (u, v) \in X \times Y$, $(x, y). (u, v) = (x * u, y *' v)$ then clearly $(X \times Y, ., (0, 0'))$ is a BZ-algebra.

Proposition 5.4.

Let $A = \{(x, \beta_A(x), \lambda_A(x)) \mid x \in X\}$ and $B = \{(x, \beta_B(x), \lambda_B(x)) \mid x \in X\}$ are intuitionistic fuzzy BZ-ideals of $(X; *, 0)$, then $A \times B$ is intuitionistic fuzzy BZ-ideal of $X \times X$.

Proof. For all $x, y \in X$,

$$\begin{aligned}
(\beta_A \times \beta_B)(0, 0) &= \min\{\beta_A(0), \beta_B(0)\} \\
&\geq \min\{\beta_A(x), \beta_B(y)\} \\
&= (\beta_A \times \beta_B)(x, y) \text{ And}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
(\lambda_A \times \lambda_B)(0, 0) &= \min\{\lambda_A(0), \lambda_B(0)\} \\
&\leq \max\{\lambda_A(x), \lambda_B(y)\} \\
&= (\lambda_A \times \lambda_B)(x, y).
\end{aligned}$$

Now let $(x_1, x_2), (y_1, y_2), (z_1, z_2) \in X \times X$, then

$$\begin{aligned}
(\beta_A \times \beta_B)((x_1, x_2) * (z_1, z_2)) &= (\beta_A \times \beta_B)(x_1 * z_1, x_2 * z_2) \\
&= \min\{\beta_A(x_1 * z_1), \beta_B(x_2 * z_2)\} \\
&\geq \min\{\min\{(\beta_A \times \beta_A)((x_1 * y_1) * z_1), (\beta_A \times \beta_A)(y_1)\}, \min\{(\beta_B \times \beta_B)((x_2 * y_2) * z_2), (\beta_B \times \beta_B)(y_2)\}\} \\
&= \min\{\min\{(\beta_A \times \beta_B)((x_1 * y_1) * z_1), ((x_2 * y_2) * z_2)\}, \min\{(\beta_A \times \beta_B)(y_1, y_2)\}\} \\
&= \min\{(\beta_A \times \beta_B)((x_1, x_2) * (y_1, y_2)) * (z_1, z_2), (\beta_A \times \beta_B)(y_1, y_2)\} \text{ and}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& (\lambda_A \times \lambda_B)((x_1, x_2) * (z_1, z_2)) = (\lambda_A \times \lambda_B)(x_1 * z_1, x_2 * z_2) \\
& = \max\{\lambda_A(x_1 * z_1), \lambda_B(x_2 * z_2)\} \\
& \leq \max\{\max\{(\lambda_A \times \lambda_A)((x_1 * y_1) * z_1), (\lambda_A \times \lambda_A)(y_1)\}, \max\{(\lambda_B \times \lambda_B)((x_2 * y_2) * z_2), (\lambda_B \times \lambda_B)(y_2)\}\} \\
= & \max\{\max\{(\lambda_A \times \lambda_B)((x_1 * y_1) * z_1), ((x_2 * y_2) * z_2)\}, \max\{(\lambda_A \times \lambda_B)(y_1, y_2)\}\} \\
& = \max\{(\lambda_A \times \lambda_B)((x_1, x_2) * (y_1, y_2)) * (z_1, z_2), (\lambda_A \times \lambda_B)(y_1, y_2)\}.
\end{aligned}$$

This completes the proof. \triangle

Definition 5.5.

Let $A = \{(x, \beta_A(x), \lambda_A(x)) \mid x \in X\}$ and $B = \{(x, \beta_B(x), \lambda_B(x)) \mid x \in X\}$ are intuitionistic fuzzy subsets of BZ-algebra $(X; *, 0)$. for $s, t \in [0, 1]$ the set

$U(\beta_A \times \beta_B, s) = \{(x, y) \in X \times X \mid \beta_A \times \beta_B(x, y) \geq s\}$ is called upper level of $U(\beta_A \times \beta_B, s)$ and $L(\lambda_A \times \lambda_B, t) = \{(x, y) \in X \times X \mid \lambda_A \times \lambda_B(x, y) \leq t\}$ is called lower level of $L(\lambda_A \times \lambda_B, t)$. \triangle

Theorem 5.6. $A = \{(x, \beta_A(x), \lambda_A(x)) \mid x \in X\}$ and $B = \{(x, \beta_B(x), \lambda_B(x)) \mid x \in X\}$ are intuitionistic fuzzy subalgebras of $(X; *, 0)$ if and only if the nonempty set upper s-level cut $U(\beta_A \times \beta_B, s)$ and the nonempty t-level cut $L(\lambda_A \times \lambda_B, t)$ are subalgebras of $X \times X$ for any $s, t \in [0, 1]$.

Proof. Let A and B are intuitionistic fuzzy subalgebras of X, therefore $(x_1, x_2), (y_1, y_2) \in X \times X$, $s, t \in [0, 1]$, such that $(x_1, x_2), (y_1, y_2) \in U(\beta_A \times \beta_B, s)$ that mean $(\beta_A \times \beta_B)(x_1, x_2) \geq s$ and $(\beta_A \times \beta_B)(y_1, y_2) \geq s$ then $(\beta_A \times \beta_B)(x_1, x_2) * (y_1, y_2) = (\beta_A \times \beta_B)(x_1 * y_1, x_2 * y_2)$
 $= \min\{\beta_A(x_1 * y_1), \beta_B(x_2 * y_2)\} \geq s$.

Therefore $(x_1 * y_1, x_2 * y_2) \in U(\beta_A \times \beta_B, s)$

$U(\beta_A \times \beta_B, s)$ is a subalgebra of $X \times X$.

In a similar way, we can prove that $L(\lambda_A \times \lambda_B, t)$ is a subalgebra of $X \times X$. This completes the proof. \triangle

Theorem 5.7. If $A = \{(x, \beta_A(x), \lambda_A(x)) \mid x \in X\}$ and

$B = \{(x, \beta_B(x), \lambda_B(x)) \mid x \in X\}$ are intuitionistic fuzzy BZ-ideals of $(X; *, 0)$, then the nonempty set upper s-level cut $U(\beta_A \times \beta_B, s)$ and the nonempty t-level cut $L(\lambda_A \times \lambda_B, t)$ are BZ-ideals of $X \times X$, for any $s, t \in [0, 1]$.

Proof. Let A and B are intuitionistic fuzzy BZ-ideals of X, therefore for any $(x, y) \in X \times X$,

$$\begin{aligned}
(\beta_A \times \beta_B)(0, 0) &= \min\{\beta_A(0), \beta_B(0)\} \\
&\geq \min\{\beta_A(x), \beta_B(y)\} \\
&= (\beta_A \times \beta_B)(x, y) \text{ and}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
(\lambda_A \times \lambda_B)(0, 0) &= \max\{\lambda_A(0), \lambda_B(0)\} \\
&\leq \max\{\lambda_A(x), \lambda_B(y)\} \\
&= (\lambda_A \times \lambda_B)(x, y), \text{ for all } s, t \in [0, 1].
\end{aligned}$$

Let $(x_1, x_2), (y_1, y_2), (z_1, z_2) \in X \times X$, such that

$((x_1, x_2) * (y_1, y_2)) * (z_1, z_2) \in U(\beta_A \times \beta_B, s)$ and $(y_1, y_2) \in U(\beta_A \times \beta_B, s)$, then

$$\begin{aligned}
(\beta_A \times \beta_B)((x_1, x_2) * (z_1, z_2)) &= (\beta_A \times \beta_B)(x_1 * z_1, x_2 * z_2) \\
&\geq \min\{(\beta_A \times \beta_B)((x_1, x_2) * (y_1, y_2)) * (z_1, z_2), (\beta_A \times \beta_B)(y_1, y_1)\} \\
&\geq \min\{s, s\} = s, \text{ therefore } ((x_1, x_2) * (z_1, z_2)) \in U(\beta_A \times \beta_B, s).
\end{aligned}$$

Hence $U(\beta_A \times \beta_B, s)$ is a BZ-ideal of $X \times X$ and

$$\begin{aligned}
(\lambda_A \times \lambda_B)((x_1, x_2) * (z_1, z_2)) &= (\lambda_A \times \lambda_B)(x_1 * z_1, x_2 * z_2) \\
&\leq \max\{(\lambda_A \times \lambda_B)((x_1, x_2) * (y_1, y_2)) * (z_1, z_2), (\lambda_A \times \lambda_B)(y_1, y_1)\} \\
&\leq \max\{t, t\} = t, \text{ therefore } ((x_1, x_2) * (z_1, z_2)) \in L(\lambda_A \times \lambda_B, t).
\end{aligned}$$

Hence $L(\lambda_A \times \lambda_B, t)$ is a BZ-ideal of $X \times X$.

\triangle

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